

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance. Part-I. Dynamic ^1H nmr Spectral Studies on Indole-1-carboxaldehydes

K. M. BISWAS*, R. N. DHARA, (Mrs) HAIMANTI MALLIK and (Miss) SUMITA ROY

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta,
92 A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

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3-Ethylindole-1-carboxaldehyde (1) and 3-phenylindole-1-carboxaldehyde (2) are shown to exist in (E) and (Z) conformations by dynamic ^1H nmr spectral studies. The coalescence temperature of the two rotamers of 2 is 23° and that in the case of 1 is 50° . This difference is probably due to the effect of the electron withdrawing phenyl group of the former and the electron donating ethyl group of the latter. The spectrum of the weighted average of the two rotamers of each of 1 and 2 is observed at elevated temperature (90°). The aldehyde proton of the (E) rotamers and H-7 of the (Z) rotamers resonate at higher frequencies than the corresponding protons of the other rotamers because of the deshielding effect of the benzene ring on the former and of the magnetic anisotropy of the carbonyl group on the latter. The barriers to internal rotation about the N—C bond of the (E) and (Z) configurations of 1 have been determined and discussed in terms of electronic effect.

ELGUERO *et al.*¹ demonstrated restricted rotation in a number of indole-1-carboxaldehydes and anisotropy effect of their carbonyl group by elegant dynamic ^1H nmr spectral studies. In continuation of our work in this area^{2,3}, we now report the results of our variable temperature ^1H nmr spectral studies on the indole-1-carboxaldehydes (1, 2 and 3), which were prepared for other purposes³⁻⁵.

- (1) R = R² = H, R¹ = Et
(2) R = R² = H, R¹ = Ph
(3) R = R¹ = Ph, R² = Me

The ^1H nmr data concerning the (E) and (Z) rotamers of 1 and 2 are described in Tables 1 and 2, and the populations of the two rotamers of 1 and the values of the barriers to their internal rotation in Tables 3 and 4

At -5° , the aldehyde proton of 1 gave rise to two sharp singlets and H-2 and H-7 of its (Z) rotamer resonated as a sharp singlet and a clean multiplet, respectively, and the signals for these two protons of its (E) conformer probably merged with those of the other aromatic protons. As the temperature was raised, their signals gradually became broad and finally coalesced to a sharp singlet and a clean

multiplet as a result of increased rate of rotation about the N—C bond and the observed spectrum was only that of the weighted average of the two conformers. The signal for H-2 of 1 could not be observed in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$, either at 23° or at 90° as it probably merged with those of the other aromatic protons. The methyl protons of 1 also appeared as a double triplet at -5° confirming the existence of two conformers at this temperature. This signal changed to a clean triplet at elevated temperatures.

Each of the signals for the aldehyde proton and H-7 of 2 in CDCl_3 appeared as a hump at 23° , presumably due to the fact that its two conformers were in a state of coalescence at this temperature (Table 2). In $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ at 23° , these signals as well as that of H-2 appeared as a hump, a broad singlet and a sharp singlet, respectively. However, at 90° the first two signals changed to a sharp singlet and a clean multiplet for the same reason as mentioned in the case of 1.

The electron donating inductive effect of the ethyl group at position 3 of 1 enhances the double bond character of the N—C bond by increasing electron density on the nitrogen atom. This results in the increase of the barrier to rotation about its N—C bond in comparison to that of 2 whose phenyl group at position 3 cannot increase electron density on the nitrogen atom as effectively as the ethyl group of 1, possibly the phenyl group rather decreases electron density on the nitrogen atom by its electron withdrawing effect^{6,7}.

The barriers to internal rotation at coalescence temperature of 1 were determined using the equation established by Shanan-Atidi and Bar-Eli^{1,7,8},

TABLE 1—¹H Nmr SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-ETHYLINDOLE-1-CARBOXALDEHYDE (1) AT VARIABLE TEMPERATURE

Solvent	Temp. °C	Conformer	Chemical shifts (δ), multiplicities and coupling constants (Hz)					
			H-2	H-7	Other Ar-H	CHO	CH ₂	CH ₃
CDCl ₃	-5	Z	7.05,s	8.32- 8.43,m	7.2- 7.7,m	9.03,s	2.70,q (8)	1.3, 2 × t (8)
		E	_____	7.2-7.7,m	_____	9.35,s	2.70,q (8)	1.3, 2 × t (8)
CDCl ₃	23	Z	6.92- 7.15,h	8.2- 8.5,h	7.23- 7.60,m	8.92- 9.18,h	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)
		E	_____	7.23-7.60,m	_____	9.22- 9.48,h	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)
CDCl ₃	35	Z	6.85- 7.05,h	8.25- 8.52,h	7.23- 7.60,m	8.85- 9.05,h	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)
		E	_____	7.23-7.60,m	_____	9.10- 9.35,h	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)
CDCl ₃	50	Coalesced form	7.20- 7.60,m	8.10- 8.47,h	7.20- 7.60,m	9.00- 9.33,h	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)
DMSO-d ₆	23	Z	7.3- 7.7,m	8.2- 8.5,h	7.3- 7.7,m	9.20- 9.35,h	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)
		E	_____	7.3-7.7,m	_____	9.5- 9.7,h	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)
DMSO-d ₆	90	Coalesced form	7.3- 7.7,m	8.18- 8.29,m	7.3- 7.7,m	9.40,s	2.69,q (8)	1.3,t (8)

 TABLE 2—¹H Nmr SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-PHENYLINDOLE-1-CARBOXALDEHYDE (2) AT VARIABLE TEMPERATURE

Solvent	Temp. °C	Chemical shifts (δ) and multiplicities			
		H-2	H-7	Other Ar-H	CHO
CDCl ₃	23	7.2-7.7,m	8.2-8.55,h	7.20-7.70,m	9.00-9.43,h
DMSO-d ₆	23	8.15,s	8.40,bs	7.40-8.00,m	9.45-9.8,h
DMSO-d ₆	90	8.15,s	8.35-8.48,m	7.55-8.05,m	9.60,s

TABLE 3—POPULATION OF CONFORMERS (Z AND E) OF 1 AT VARIABLE TEMPERATURE IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	Temp °C	Conformer	Percentage
CDCl ₃	-5	Z	55
		E	45
CDCl ₃	23	Z	64
		E	36
CDCl ₃	35	Z	72
		E	28
DMSO-d ₆	23	Z	70
		E	30
DMSO-d ₆	90	Coalesced form	100

as the rotamers (E) and (Z) of 1 were not equally populated. However, the calculations were based on the values of X corresponding to ΔP published recently⁹, which are reported to provide more accurate results⁹ than the graphic procedure of the former workers. The higher barrier to internal rotation for 1 compared to those of indole-1-carboxaldehyde¹ (*viz.* 61.5 and 63.1 kJ mol⁻¹) can also be explained in terms of electronic effect (*vide supra*), and this is supported by the fact that the values of the barrier to internal rotation of 1 compare favourably with those of 3-methylindole-1-carboxaldehyde¹ (*viz.* 68.1 and 70.0 kJ mol⁻¹). The rate constants k_A and k_B were calculated using the equation of Shanani-Atidi and Bar-Eli⁷ but the values of X corresponding to Δp^9 were used. The values of k tally well with those of *p*-methoxy-*N,N*-dimethylthiobenzamide¹⁰.

The spectrum of 5-methyl-2,3-diphenylindole-1-carboxaldehyde (3) did not show any change on rerecording⁸ at lower temperature (23°, DMSO-d₆) or at higher temperature (90°, DMSO-d₆), probably

TABLE 4—BARRIERS TO INTERNAL ROTATION IN 3-ETHYLINDOLE-1-CARBOXALDEHYDE (1)

Solvent	Rotamer (E) population %	Signal observed	T ₀ K	$\Delta\nu$ Hz	τ	k_A s ⁻¹	k_B s ⁻¹	ΔG_0^* kJ mol ⁻¹
CDCl ₃	45	CHO	323	28.8	9.446 × 10 ⁻³	48	58	E→Z 68.3 ± 0.5 Z→E 68.9 ± 0.5

because the coalescence temperature of its two rotamers lies below 23°.

Experimental

Nmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer equipped with a variable temperature controller. The temperature could be measured accurately to $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The chemical shifts are given in ppm relative either to TMS or DSS as internal reference; coupling constants are given in Hz, and the ΔG_c^* values in kJ mol^{-1} . The preparation of the compounds (1-3) has been recorded elsewhere³.

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